

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395597>
UDK 621.318.2

APPROACHES TO THE SELECTION OF INITIAL MAGNETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE CALCULATION OF A PERMANENT MAGNET AND EVALUATION OF CALCULATION WEBSITES

A.T. Hovhannisyan,

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Leading Researcher,

K.R. Yenokyan,

junior researcher,

National Polytechnic University of Armenia,

Yerevan

Annotation: This work presents the relationship between magnetic properties, and selection criteria in the process of calculation of permanent magnet parameters as well as the accuracy of information retrieval of technical data, the significance of output parameters in magnetic measurements, and the evaluation of online computational websites according to calculation accuracy. The data of investigations, analysis, and conclusions on the example of calculation of the magnetic field induction inside and outside the working points and magnetic field induction of cylindrical permanent magnet magnetized along the length.

Keywords: permanent magnet, magnetic parameter, initial parameters

Introduction

One of the aims of permanent magnet (PM) implementations is providing the needed magnitude of the magnetic field in the a air area outside the magnet (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 - Polarization and dimensional designations of PM

For the calculation of the magnetic parameters of the PM the main initial parameters are: H_{cB} coercion force by induction, B_r remaining induction, $(BH)_m$ product with the maximum energy.

There are multiple websites where the above mentioned parameters are given by the brand of the PM. Research has shown that there are differences in data given in the sources, as well as some of the in the dimensions are given in intervals and/or conditions. For instance, for N38 PM in [2] are given $H_{cB}=(836\div 891)\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,22\div 1,26)T$, $(BH)_m=(279\div 302)\cdot 10^3 J/m^3$, in [3] $H_{cB}\geq 899\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,22\div 1,25)T$, $(BH)_m=(287\div 310)\cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

There are numerous websites which calculate some magnetic parameters of a PM, as well as magnetic field induction in each point of the length axis [4÷10].

Proposed tasks

1. Define the logical conditions of choosing the initial parameters.
2. Research the influence of the values of parameter's intervals on the values of the working points of the PM.
3. Analyse the accuracy of the calculation websites.

Mathematical apparatus for solving the problem

1. The characteristics of $B(-H)$ PM are plotted on the plane of the coordinate axis in accordance with the following known expression (Fig. 2)

$$B_i = B_r \frac{H_{cB} - H_i}{H_{cB} - \gamma_c H_i}, \quad (1)$$

where the values of H_i are picked from the range 0 to H_{cB} , a γ_c the convexity coefficient of the material PM, the value of which is within $0 < \gamma_c < 1$ and is determined as follows

$$\gamma_c = 2 \sqrt{\frac{H_{cB} B_r}{(BH)_m}} - \frac{H_{cB} B_r}{(BH)_m} \tag{2}$$

The initial data should be of dimension so that the following condition is true for the γ_c

$$0 < \gamma_c < 1, \tag{3}$$

that is, the characteristic $B(-H)$ is between the lines $B_i = B_r$ (if $\gamma_c = 1$) and $B_i = B_r \frac{H_{cB} - H_i}{H_{cB}}$ (if $\gamma_c = 0$).

Figure 3 - $B(-H)$ characteristic, boundaries are located and working points PM

To have the condition (3) the following condition should be provided among the parameters:

$$\frac{H_{cB} B_r}{4} < (BH)_m < H_{cB} B_r. \tag{4}$$

If initial two data points are chosen, then the third one can be calculated by the following expressions:

$$B_r \approx 2 \sqrt{\mu_0 (BH)_m}, \tag{5}$$

$$(BH)_m \approx \frac{B_r^2}{4 \mu_0}, \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{(BH)_m}{B_r} < H_{cB} < 4 \frac{(BH)_m}{B_r}. \tag{7}$$

2. The value of the permeability coefficient m_p of the PM form is determined [1].

For a cylindrical PM with a $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}}$ ratio of the 0,1÷10 interval (except when $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} = 1$), it is suggested to use the following expression

$$m_p = 2,46 \left(\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} \right)^{-1,32}. \quad (8)$$

When $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} = 1$, $m_p = 3$. (9)

3. The parameters of the PM in the cross section of the neutral 00 are determined by the famous expressions (Figure 1).

Magnetic induction

$$B_0 = \frac{k_0 - \sqrt{k_0^2 - 4\mu_0 \gamma_c m_p H_{cB} B_r}}{2\gamma_c}, \quad (10)$$

where $k_0 = (B_r + \mu_0 m_p H_{cB})$, $\mu_0 = 4\pi 10^{-7} \text{Hn/m}$.

Magnetic field voltage

$$H_0 = H_{cB} \frac{B_0 - B_r}{\gamma_c B_0 - B_r}. \quad (11)$$

4. Calculation of magnetic induction at the N PM pole

$$B_N = (\mu_0 H_0 + B_0) \frac{\ell_{PM}}{\sqrt{4\ell_{PM}^2 + d_{PM}^2}}. \quad (12)$$

5. The magnetic induction of scattering is determined

$$B_\sigma = B_0 - B_N. \quad (13)$$

6. The scattering coefficient by magnetic induction is determined

$$k_\sigma = \frac{B_0}{B_N}. \quad (14)$$

7. The magnitude of the induction B_a at point a at a distance x from the pole N (Figure 1)

$$B_a = (\mu_0 H_0 + B_N) \left[\frac{\ell_{PM} + x}{\sqrt{4(\ell_{PM} + x)^2 + d_{PM}^2}} - \frac{x}{\sqrt{4x^2 + d_{PM}^2}} \right]. \quad (15)$$

Research results

A. For the proposed tasks 1. and 2., a N38 PM of sizes $\ell_{<U>}=10\text{mm}$, $d_{<U>}=30\text{mm}$ has been researched with the generalized marginal parameters according to sources [2, 3] being $H_{cB}=(836\div 899)\cdot 10^3 \text{A/m}$, $B_r=(1,22\div 1,26)\text{T}$, $(BH)_m=(279\div 310)\cdot 10^3 \text{J/m}^3$.

The relative errors of the marginal parameters are correspondingly 7,0%, 3,2%, and 10%.

The values of operating points and other magnetic parameters of the PM for various combinations of initial data are given in the Table 1.

For $n=5$, the string γ_c received a negative value (-0,03), which is unacceptable, since, for example, condition (4) is not satisfied: $\frac{H_{cB}B_r}{4} = 283 \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$, and the calculated value $(BH)_m = 279 \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

The maximum relative error of the magnetic parameters of the PM operating points is about 7,3%, which corresponds to the minimum ($n=2$) and maximum ($n=6$) initial values.

Table 1 - Magnetic parameters of the PM with different combinations of initial data

n	B_r T	H_{cB} kA/m	$(BH)_m$ kJ/m ³	γ_c	m_p	B_0 T	H_0 kA/m	B_N T	B_σ T	K_σ
1	1.22	836	279	0.168	0.577	0.421	581.178	0.319	0.102	1.319
2	1.26	836	279	0.111	0.577	0.42	578.965	0.318	0.101	1.319
3	1.22	899	279	0.034	0.577	0.428	590.691	0.324	0.104	1.319
4	1.22	836	310	0.338	0.577	0.441	608.182	0.334	0.107	1.319
5	1.26	899	279	-0.03	0.577	0.427	588.651	0.323	0.103	1.319
6	1.22	899	310	0.224	0.577	0.449	619.312	0.34	0.109	1.319
7	1.26	836	310	0.289	0.577	0.439	605.707	0.333	0.106	1.319
8	1.26	899	310	0.169	0.577	0.447	617.01	0.339	0.108	1.319

B. For the research of the proposed task 3. N38 PM with sizes $\ell_{PM}=10mm$, $d_{PM}=30mm$ has been chosen.

The directory source suggests that $H_{cB}=(836\div 891) \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,22\div 1,26)T$, $(BH)_m=(279\div 302) \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$ [2].

For the calculation $H_{cB}=836 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=1,22T$, $(BH)_m=279 \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$ has been chosen.

The data received from the mentioned mathematical apparatus has been taken as a base, which, compared to the experimental one, showed better results as the maximum relative error was 2,4% [1-10].

The analysis of $B_a(x)$ on computational [4÷10] sources and their relative error compared to [1] are given in the table 2.

Conclusion.

1. Use expressions (5-7) when choosing the calculated initial data of the PM, where it is necessary to ensure conditions (3) and (4).
2. The interval error of the PM's informative data has slight impact on PM's magnetic parameters and no special approach is needed.
3. Out of all the calculational websites, [10] gives out the best result.

Table 2 - Research results on $B_a(x)$ according to calculation websites

Bib.	X, mm	0	10	20	30	40	50
[1]	B_a, mT	318,81	128,99	49,51	21,98	11,43	6,46
[4-6]	B_a, mT	338,37	149,63	57,60	25,56	13,11	7,51
	$\delta, \%$	-5,7	-13,8	-14,0	-14,0	-12,8	-13,9
[7]	B_a, mT	386,0	27,23	12,18	6,60	4,23	2,95
	$\delta, \%$	-17,4	81,8	80,4	233,0	170,2	118,9
[8]	B_a, mT	225,56	134,17	71,49	42,35	27,65	20,14
	$\delta, \%$	41,3	-3,8	-30,7	-48,1	-58,6	-67,9
[9]	B_a, mT	349,5	154,5	59,5	26,4	13,5	7,8
	$\delta, \%$	-8,8	-16,5	-16,8	-16,7	-15,3	-17,2
[10]	B_a, mT	317,75	140,51	54,09	24,0	12,31	7,05
	$\delta, \%$	0,3	-8,2	-8,5	-8,4	-7,1	-3,6

Gratitude

This work was supported by the RA MESCS State Committee of Science, in the frames of the research project «Automated Systems and Modeling» research base laboratory.

Bibliography

[1] Hovhannisyan A.T. Mathematical apparatus for calculating a cylindrical permanent magnet magnetized along the length based on usecase // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 6-2(30). 62-72 с. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/> (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[2] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: www.technomagproduct.nethouse.ru Постоянные магниты (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[3] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: http://imlab.narod.ru/M_Fields/Magnet_Models/Magnet_Models.htm – (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[4] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: www.Формулы_для_расчета_постоянных_магнитов. (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[5] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: [www. Magnetic Circuit Design Guide | Tech Notes - TDK Product Center](http://www.Magnetic_Circuit_Design_Guide_Tech_Notes_TDK_Product_Center) – (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[6] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://magnet-sdm.de/magnetische-flussdichte-rechner/> (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[7] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: www.chat.openai.com (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[8] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: www.femm.info/wiki/HomePage (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[9] Title from the screen [Electronic resource] – URL: www.kjmagnetics.com/calculator.asp Magnet Calculator - K&J Magnetics (date of access: 06/21/2023)

[10] [Electronic resource] – URL: www.magnetfabrik.de/en/knowledge/magnet-calculator (date of access: 06/21/2023)

© *A.T. Hovhannisyán, K.R. Yenokyan, 2023*

Поступила в редакцию 16.08.2023

Принята к публикации 31.08.2023

Для цитирования:

Hovhannisyán A.T., Yenokyan K.R. Approaches to the selection of initial magnetic parameters for the calculation of a permanent magnet and evaluation of calculation websites // *Инновационные научные исследования*. 2023. № 8-1(31). С. 34-40. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>